

**SERVICE QUALITY, TOURIST SATISFACTION
AND REVISIT INTENTION :
STUDY OF VISITORS IN JAIPUR**

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ABSTRACT

Tourism and hospitality industry is primarily a service industry where the entire focus of service provider is to satisfy customer's expectation, encouraging them for revisit and positive word of mouth. This study aims to investigate the relation of service quality with the customer satisfaction and revisit intention at a tourist destination. This paper established a relation between customer satisfaction with service quality motivate for revisiting the Jaipur recently declared World Heritage City. Therefore, judgment of quality by consumer should be given the highest priority and their decision regarding the quality of service should be welcome by the hosts. A quantitative study using questionnaire of 320 responses were analyzed to generate findings. The result from the research study showed the constructs like destination facilities, destination attractiveness, price affordability and staff behavior contribute directly in satisfaction of tourists and their intention to visit the site again. This paper also highlights the management strategies in tourism industry with future implication to enrich the experience of tourist visiting Jaipur.

Keywords : Jaipur, Revisit Intention, Service Quality, Tourist Satisfaction

Introduction

Service Quality from a customer perspective is considered as a significant factors in deciding the satisfaction and success of Destination Management Organization and Stakeholders. This has increased the attraction of practitioner and researchers to study tourist perception of Service Quality at the destination and how it impacts the satisfaction and intention to revisit the place. Numerous authors supports satisfaction of customers is an outcome of perceived service quality (Cao, 2015; Singh, 2017) and it results in revisiting the destination along with recommending to others (Chen, 2007; Puri & Singh, 2020; Ryu et al., 2012).

Various studies have been found on destination and tourist satisfaction but very few studies have discussed Service quality and revisit intention of Tourists to Jaipur. To fill this gap, study is conducted to investigate Service quality and Satisfaction at a destination. The main

objective of the study are to measure service quality at Jaipur and its impact on Tourist Satisfaction and Revisit Intention.

The paper starts with reviewing literature on Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Revisit Intention and Relationship among them. It is followed by methodology, data analysis and findings. The last section are discussions, conclusions and implications.

Review of Literature

Concept of Service Quality

Parasuraman et al. (1985) described 'service quality' as "the degree and direction of discrepancy between customer's perceptions and expectations". Also they described "perceived service quality" as "the gap between customers' expectations and perceptions. Lehtinen and Lehtinen (1982) claimed that "service quality is delivered when there is the interaction between a customer and the service. Many researchers have

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investigated the research on service quality (**Gronroos, 1978; Lehtinen&Lehtinen, 1982; Lewis and Booms, 1983;Puri& Singh, 2018**). There are 3 important characteristics of service quality:

- Service quality is difficult to evaluate whereas it is easy to measure quality of goods for consumers.
- The consumer expectation with perception is evaluated to know the gap between them.
- The process of service delivery is important for the evaluation of service quality which helps to measure the outcome of service quality.

Concept of Satisfaction

Satisfaction is an indispensable factor that firms want to obtain from consumers for continued existence in market. Over the time period with the viewpoint of researchers, there are two new methods of satisfaction: "Transactional and Overall satisfaction". Transactional Satisfaction refers to an idea about any purchase related event whereas overall satisfaction refers to the hoarded knowledge exhibited the actual customer's gathering simulation for that particular products and services.

Definition of Consumer Satisfaction

Kotler (2012) defined customer satisfaction "as the level of one's feelings after comparing perceived performance or results compared with expectations".

Definition of Tourist Satisfaction

Chen and Tsai (2007) defined "tourist satisfaction as a positive perception or feeling that tourists develop or acquire by engaging in recreational activities and is expressed as the degree of pleasure derived from such experiences.

Relationship Between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Dmitrovic et al. (2009) confirmed that the higher tourist satisfaction can lead to higher profit and revenue for service providers. Customer satisfaction plays an important role and is a major factor in determining the level of tourist loyalty. Moreover, the relationship between customer satisfaction and revisit intentions in the tourism sector has been a basis of concern for both academician and practitioner due to its positive impact on hospitality (**Ryuet al., 2012**).

H1: There exists positive correlation between service

quality between Service Quality and Customer satisfaction

Concept of Revisit Intention

Many previous research from scholars like (Engeset&Elvekrok, 2015; Prayag& Ryan, 2012) revealed that if tourists are satisfied they will recommend the destination to others. In current industry the concept of revisit intention plays a significant role where there is an increase in the customer loyalty.

According to **Kozak (2001)** "Tourist revisit intention is an actual response to certain behaviours which generally refers to the tourist willingness to visit a certain destinations or other destinations in the same country". According to Li et al (2008) many scholars from tourism industry described tourism as a "search for novel experiences that are distinct from the routine experiences encountered at home". The findings revealed that image of the destination and tourist satisfaction had a significant effect on intention to revisit.

Relationship between Service Quality and Revisit Intention

Pritchard (2003) analyzed that revisit intention in tourism sector is one of the important concept to attract the tourists and for the economic growth of the country. Various studies explained that most of the tourists likely to visit the same destination again and contribute largely in the financial status of the nation. Oliver (1980) revealed that if customer is satisfied it also increase the revisit intention in future. According to Cao, DiPietro, &Kock(2015) loyalty is one of the main reason for tourist revisit intention. Revisit intention in international tourism can induce positive word of mouth and recommend the destination to relatives or friends (Chen, C., & Tsai, D.,2007)

H2: There exists positive correlation between Service Quality and Revisit Intention

Methodology

The study follows deductive approach using quantitative methods measuring tourist perception of Service Quality, Satisfaction from destination and Intention to revisit the site again. A structured questionnaire was prepared which includes constructs measured fro the items adopted from various literature.

Items related to service quality were taken from study of Narayan et al. (2008), Zakaria et al. (2010), Lam and Zhang (1999), Adinegra (2018) and Nithila (2014). The six items for satisfaction construct was measured through Aliman (2014), Canny (2013); whereas five items related to Revisit Intention were measured through items from studies of Zabkar et al. (2010). The English and Hindi (translated from English) questionnaire were sent to tourists visiting Jaipur “Pink City”. A pink and walled city Jaipur declared as a UNESCO World Heritage site in 2019. It has a glorious history of great Rajputs and their ancestral magnificent architectural masterpiece monuments. The World Heritage City status boosts Domestic and International tourism, strengths the local economy to promote its indigenous culture and traditions of city. The questionnaire was given to 360 respondents, 337 were received, 17 were found incomplete and 320 were found fit for study. The research was conducted during October to December, 2019. The items in the questionnaire was measured using 5-items likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The results of

the study was analyzed by SPSS25.0 applying Univariate and Multivariate analysis. Analysis and Results are discussed in the next sections.

Data Analysis and Interpretations

The responses were collected and analyzed from the questionnaire which was divided into two parts. The first section dealt with demographic details of the respondents explained in Table 1.

In the survey questionnaire 176 Males and 144 Females responses were received. Most of them were less than age of less than 27 years (127) and 25-40 years (98) followed by 40 to 55 years (66) and more than 55 years (29). 211 visitors were Indian and 109 foreigners. Most of the respondents have their Intermediate (120) and Graduate (82) degree in their education. Highest number of visitors arrived were from government job (108) followed by students (79) and Private Sector (77). From, the respondents profile it was observed that most of visitors were visiting the place first or second time with their major purpose of Vacation (139), Business (69), Participating in Conference (56) and Visiting their Friends and Relatives (56).

Gender	Frequency	Education	Frequency
Male	176	High School	72
Female	144	Intermediate	120
Total	320	Graduate	82
Age	Frequency	Post Graduate or Higher	46
less than 25 years	127	Total	320
25 to 40 years	98	Occupation	Frequency
40 to 55 years	66	Students	79
more than 55 years	29	Govt. Sector	108
Nationality	Frequency	Private Sector	77
Indian	211	Self-employed	43
Foreigner	109	others	13
Total	320	Total	320
No. of Visit	Frequency	Purpose of Visit	Frequency
Firsttime	204	Business	69
Second Times	97	Vacation	139
Third Time	15	Conference/Meeting	56
more than 3 times	4	Visitors, Friends and Relatives	56
Total	320		

Table 1 : Demographic Details

Reliability test was carried out to measure out to measure internal consistency among item that comprise a construct from the scale (Singh&Ranjan, 2019). Table

2,ehhibits that internal consistencies measured through Cronbach's alpha values for all constructs exceeds minimum acceptable values of 0.60 (Phan and Matsui, 2012) indicating that constructs are consistent.

Constructs	Code	No. Of Items	Cronbach's alpha	Mean	S.D.
Destination Facilities	DF	17	0.78	3.72	0.67
Destination Attractiveness	DA	09	0.82	3.54	0.70
Price Affordability	PA	04	0.79	3.38	0.72
Staff Behavior	SB	12	0.81	3.76	0.74
Customer Satisfaction	CS	06	0.87	3.63	0.73
Revisit Intention	RI	05	0.84	3.78	0.79

Table 2: Reliability Test

Content Validity of the constructs were confirmed from literature review and opinion of subject experts from Hotel and Tourism industry. Construct Validity was examined by conducting Factor analysis of summated construct for scale through Table 3(a) and Table 3(b). The KMO and Bartlett's test measured sampling adequacy for table 3 (a) 0.820 for service quality items and 0.936 for satisfaction and revisit intention construct whose value were greater than >0.05 with significant value (p=0.00). Table 3(a) presents Cumulative of Variance explains

68.85 % from four factors. ByPrincipal Component Analysis and Varimax with Kaiser Normalisation method, four components were extracted with eigenvalue more than one in 42 Service Quality items named as - **Destination Facilities (DF), Destination Attractiveness (DA), Price Affordability (PA) and Staff Behaviour (SB)**. While two components were extracted from 11 Satisfaction items named as **Customer Satisfaction (CS) and Revisit Intention (RI)**.Table 3(b) presents 82.60% from two factors.

Component Matrix ^a				
	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Appealing accommodation facilities	.822			
Availability of banking/ATM facilities/foreign exchange	.861			
Availability of internet facilities	.848			
Hygiene level at site	.840			
Local transport service	.844			
Traffic maintenance	.841			
Sanitation facilities	.826			
Security system at hotels	.853			
Variety of items in menu	.829			
Error-free service	.827			
Availability of parking	.819			
Quality of food	.816			
Frequency of transport service	.811			

Availability of entertainment facilities	.749			
Cleanliness of hotels	.736			
Availability of health facilities	.702			
Location of hotels	.722			
Rajasthan Has Historical and Cultural Sites		.630		
Signage & information at sites		.689		
Availability of Sight Seeing at the Destination		.832		
Security at the tourist spots		.712		
Availability of tourist information centers		.640		
Interesting night life		.858		
Amusement & theme parks		.873		
Visual appearance of hotels		.819		
Availability of restaurants		.804		
Safe & secure transactions			.858	
Price of food & beverage			.838	
Price of transport			.838	
Price offered by hotels			.822	
Confidence in staff behavior				0.864
Responsiveness of staff to requests				0.858
Employees were keen to solve problems				0.821
Eigenvalues	6.27	3.01	2.63	2.08
% of Variance	42.243	10.320	8.763	7.324
Cumulative Variance	42.243	52.563	61.326	68.652
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.				

Table 3 (a) Factor Analysis of Service quality items

Component Matrix ^a		
	Component	
	1	2
My choice to purchase this trip to Rajasthan was a wise one	.738	
I have truly enjoyed this visit to Rajasthan	.790	
The visit was exactly what I needed	.829	
I feel good about my decision to visit this destination	.749	

My visit to this place offer good value for money	.812	
Overall, I am satisfied with my decision to visit the tourist destination	.787	
I considered Rajasthan as my first choice		.699
I will revisit Rajasthan in future.		.742
I will highly recommended Rajasthan to others.		.706
I will say positive things about this destination to other people		.853
I would like to revisit this destination more often		.827
Eigenvalues	7.595	1.571
% of Variance	44.694	37.907
Cumulative Variance	44.694	82.602
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

Table 3 (b) Factor Analysis of Satisfaction and Revisit Intention items.

Multiple Regression Analysis was performed for extent of Service Quality items affecting Satisfaction at Destination and Intention to Revisit the destination through Enter Method which was used for Independent

Variables (SQ) to Multiple Regression Analysis. The results of Service Quality with Satisfaction (CS) and Revisit Intention (RI) are presented in Table 4(a) and 4 (b) respectively.

Independent Variables	b	S.E.	Beta	T	Sig.
Constant	1.892	0.132		8.427	
DF	0.093	0.031	0.086	4.263	0.000
DA	0.081	0.021	0.079	3.412	0.001
PA	0.059	0.022	0.053	2.015	0.000
SB	0.053	0.018	0.047	1.832	0.000

R²=0.683, Adjusted R²=0.672, S.E. = 0.583, F-ratio =67.714 (p<0.000)

Table 4 (a) : Regression Analysis Results Service Quality and Satisfaction

It was observed that Customer Satisfaction with Destination service quality was statistically significant with a total 68.3 % variance of Service Quality (R²=0.683) with customer satisfaction. Adjusted R² achieved was 0.672. The equation from Multiple

Regression analysis is as follows:

$$\text{Customer Satisfaction} = 1.892 + (0.093) \text{ DF} + (0.081) \text{ DA} + (0.059) \text{ PA} + (0.053) \text{ SB}$$

The results presents all factors as a significant predictor of Tourist Satisfaction (p<0.05)

Independent Variables	b	S.E.	Beta	T	Sig.
Constant	2.210	0.202		10.243	
DF	0.091	0.079	0.089	4.312	0.000
DA	0.090	0.062	0.078	3.119	0.000
PA	0.052	0.013	0.052	1.054	0.000
SB	0.048	0.019	0.031	4.012	0.001

R²=0.642, Adjusted R²=0.629, S.E. =0.052, F-ratio= 64.243 (p<0.000)

Table 4 (b) : Regression Analysis Results Service Quality and Revisit Intention

The Intention to Revisit destination with Destination Service Quality was statistically significant with total 64.2 % variance of Service Quality ($R^2=0.642$) with Revisit Intention. Adjusted R^2 achieved was 0.629. The equation was thus formed here as:

$$\text{Revisit Intention} = 2.210 + (0.091) \text{DF} + (0.090) \text{DA} + (0.052) \text{PA} + (0.048) \text{SB}$$

	Service Quality	Customer Satisfaction	Revisit Intention
Service Quality	1	0.720	0.683
Customer Satisfaction		1	0.624
Revisit Intention			1

Table 5: Correlation Analysis Results

Through analysis, it was positive correlation between Service Quality and Tourist Satisfaction. ($r=0.72$, $p=0.000$). Similarly, positive correlation was

The results presents all factors as a significant predictor of Revisit Intention ($p<0.05$)

To examine whether there is connection between Service Quality with Satisfaction and Revisit Intention is described in Table 5. Correlation analysis was carried out through Pearson's Correlation Coefficient.

observed between Service Quality and Intention to Revisit ($r=0.68$, $p=0.000$).

Results from Hypothesis

<u>Hypothesis</u>	<u>Result</u>
<i>H1: There exists positive correlation between service quality between Service Quality and Customer satisfaction</i>	Supported
<i>H2: There exists positive correlation between Service Quality and Revisit Intention</i>	Supported

Conclusion and Future Implication

This paper highlights the relationship among customer satisfaction, service quality and revisit intention. The four constructs which explained service quality dimensions over destination satisfaction were positively correlated with dimensions of Satisfaction and Revisit intentions mentioned in this study. If we take into account that tourists when selecting a destination for their visit and stay experience, it is crucial from service provider to invest in service quality to enhance the experience of tourists for their satisfaction and visiting a place again.

The research could focus on evaluating revisit intention and satisfaction from the demographic characteristics of respondents. The nature of respondents and study site is dynamic, so it can generate other factors possible for evaluating Service Quality. Also the nature of

study was limited to Jaipur city of Rajasthan. Further, study can be covered with these constructs in large geographical areas and different cultures to evaluate satisfaction of tourists and their intention to revisit the destination.

The scope and significance of this study become vital for the tourism policy makers and tour planners for making the destination more attractive for enriching tourist experience in terms of tourist satisfaction and visitors to plan the visit to destination again.

References :

- Adinegara, G. N. J. (2018). Modeling of Tourist Satisfaction in Bali. *Binus Business Review*, 9(3), 261-276.
- Aliman, N. K., Hashim, S. M., Wahid, S. D. M., & Harudin, S. (2014). Tourist expectation, perceived quality and destination image: Effects

on perceived value and satisfaction of tourists visiting langkawi Island, Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Business and Management*, 2(3).

- Asubonteng, P, McCleary, KJ & Swan, JE 1996, 'SERVQUAL revisited: a critical review of service quality', *The Journal of Services Marketing*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 62-81.
- Canny, I. U. (2013). An empirical investigation of service quality, tourist satisfaction and future behavioral intentions among domestic local tourist at Borobudur Temple. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 4(2), 86.
- Cao, Y., DiPietro, R., & Kock, G. (2015). Customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions: The case of Aruba--small island nation. *Hospitality Review*, 31(4), 41–68.
- Chen, C., & Tsai, D. (2007). How destination image and evaluative factors affect behavioral intentions. *Tourism Management*, 28(4), 1115-1122.
- Dmitrović, T., Knežević Cvelbar, L., Kolar, T., Makovec Brenčič, M., Ograjensek, I. and Žabkar, V. (2009), "Conceptualizing tourist satisfaction at the destination level", *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*, Vol. 3 No. 2, pp. 116-126. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17506180910962122>
- Engeset, M. G., & Elvekrok, I. (2015). Authentic Concepts: Effects on Tourist Satisfaction. *Journal of Travel Research*, 54(4), 456–466. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287514522876>
- Gronroos, C. (1978), "A Service-Oriented Approach to Marketing of Services," *European Journal of Marketing*, 12 (no. 8), 588-601. (1982), *Strategic Management and Marketing in the Service Sector*, Helsingfors: Swedish School of Economics and Business Administration.
- Gronroos, C. (1990), "Service Management: A Management Focus for Service Competition", *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 6-14. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09564239010139125>.
- Kotler, P. (2012). *Kotler on marketing*. Simon and Schuster.
- Kozak, M. (2001), "Repeaters' behavior at two distinct destinations", *Annals of Tourism Research*, Vol. 28 No. 3, pp. 784-807.
- Lam, T., & Zhang, H. Q. (1999). Service quality of travel agents: the case of travel agents in Hong Kong. *Tourism management*, 20(3), 341-349.
- Lehtinen, Uolevi and Jarmo R. Lehtinen (1982), "Service Quality: A Study of Quality Dimensions," unpublished working paper, Helsinki: Service Management Institute, Finland OY.
- Lewis, Robert C. and Bernard H. Booms (1983), "The Marketing Aspects of Service Quality," in *Emerging Perspectives on Services Marketing*, L. Berry, G. Shostack, and G. Upah, eds., Chicago: American Marketing, 99-107.
- Li, X., Cheng, C.-K., Kim, H. and Petrick, J. (2008), "A systematic comparison of first-time and repeat visitors via a two-phase survey", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 29, pp. 278-93.
- Narayan, B., Rajendran, C., & Sai, L. P. (2008). Scales to measure and benchmark service quality in tourism industry. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*.
- Nithila, R. C. J. (2014). Service quality analysis and its implication—A study on tourism services in Kodaikannal. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 2(12), 1871-1879.
- Oliver, R. L. (1980). A cognitive model of the antecedents and consequences of satisfaction decisions. *Journal of marketing research*, 17(4), 460-469.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithami, V. & Berry L. L. (1985), "A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research", *Journal of Marketing*, 49 (Fall): 41-50.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithami, V. & Berry, L.L. (1988), "SERVQUAL: a Multiple Item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Quality", *Journal of Retailing*, 64 (1): 12-40
- Phan, C. A., & Matsui, Y. (2012). Contribution of total productive maintenance to quality performance: Empirical evidence from Japanese

manufacturing plants. *The Journal of Japanese Operations Management and Strategy*, 3(1), 38-54.

- Prayag, G., & Ryan, C. (2012). Antecedents of Tourists' Loyalty to Mauritius: The Role and Influence of Destination Image, Place Attachment, Personal Involvement, and Satisfaction. *Journal of Travel Research*, 51(3), 342–356. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287511410321>
- Pritchard, M.P., 2003. The attitudinal and behavioral consequences of destination performance. *Touris. Anal.*, 8: 61-73.
- Puri, G., & Singh, K. (2018). The role of service quality and customer satisfaction in tourism industry: A review of SERVQUAL Model. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, VOL. 5(4), 745-751 Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343826894_Impact_of_uncontrolled_Marketing_on_Tourists_and_Tourist_destinations_A_Theoretical_Analysis [accessed Oct 11 2020].
- Puri, G., & Singh, K. (2020). A CONCEPTUAL STUDY OF SERVICE QUALITY, TOURIST SATISFACTION AND REVISIT INTENTION Review of Literature. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(9), 1–14.
- Ryu, K., Lee, H. and Gon Kim, W. (2012), "The influence of the quality of the physical environment, food, and service on restaurant image, customer perceived value, customer satisfaction, and behavioral intentions", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 24(2), 200-223. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596111211206141>
- Singh, S. J. (2017). Customer Perception and Application of Gap Model in Service Quality of Star-Category hotels in Varanasi. *Avahan: A Journal on Hospitality and Tourism*, 5(1), 34-46.
- Singh, S. V., & Ranjan, R. (2019). Online travel portal and their effect on travel agency: A study on outbound visitors of Varanasi. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, 6(2), 387-393.
- Žabkar, V., Brenčič, M. M., & Dmitrović, T. (2010). Modelling perceived quality, visitor satisfaction and behavioural intentions at the destination level. *Tourism management*, 31(4), 537-546.
- Zakaria, Z., Hamid, A. C., Karim, Z. A., & Daud, N. M. (2010). Tourists' Expectations and Perceptions on the Service Quality in Malaysian Tourism Industry. *Global Business and Management Research: An International Journal*, 1(3), 69.
- Zeithaml, VA (1988). Consumer perceptions of price, quality and value: a means-end model and synthesis of evidence. *Journal of Marketing*, 52(3), 2-22.

